

THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS
EFFECT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH

Ergasheva Durdona

Annotation. This goal, the development of the tourism sector of Uzbekistan and its economy are described in the definition of growth. The tourism sector is one of the important opportunities that provide significant information to the economic, social and cultural development of the country. The child of Uzbekistan with its historical heritage, natural landscapes, and spiritual views has great potential for the development of the species. The work analyzes the strategies adopted for the development of the tourism industry, the projects implemented in practice and their results. It also considers the contribution of tourism to domestic and foreign economic growth. Khusan proposes to create jobs of the tourism sector, develop infrastructure, recycle the income of the residents of the neighborhood and recycle foreign investment. At the end of the work, recommendations were made for the development of tourism in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: tourism industry, economy growth, globalization process, strategies, infrastructure, extreme tourism,

In all countries with a modern economy, information is provided about each sphere, network, and guidance. Chunonchi, they consider the Review, contributing to the development of the country's economy, the improvement of the standard of living of the population and several other opportunities. The tourism sector is the largest component of the service sector. Travel is a form of travel in which people travel to places in environments typical of Chief magsads, such as getting a dam, doing business, studying other folk culture. In modern times, there are several types of Tourism. Summary, type of advertising, type of business, type of excursion, extreme type, cultural and educational type, VIP type, ordering of rain-valued resorts, ecotourism, type of mountain, ethnic type, sea type and headlands.

Tourism are those who have the opportunity to receive from each species a self-sufficient service of courage, a sense of self-confidence, strength of courage and enlightenment, victory in difficulties and home-made upbringing, instructive her-desires. At this point, it is worth noting that one gator in tourism mamalakati showed an active definition of the mintage to economy and culture. For example, a close garden with the development of a tourism development system, trade, socio-domestic, cultural, medical services to tourists. Tourism is a fast-growing sector compared to other sectors, as this sector is an area for our country that can compete with the demand of large investments. Other areas, air from place to place, rail, road transport, catering and trade stations, guests can develop the tour freely if there are tourist facilities in the other place. According to experts in the field of tourism, in the 21st century it will become the leading industry in the world economy. Now around the world, the main third place is occupied by the automotive industry and oil refining industry. This sector has passed through world industry and agriculture. Another reason for the rapid development of tourism is that it does not require a high level of large scientific research costs and technology that costs a lot of joy. However, tourism requires the development of other areas. Thanks to this, many service sectors with this sector should develop inextricably with each other.

In reconstruction and repair, which is in adapting them to the requirements of ham world standards. An example of this is the dozens of special guests built in the city of Samarkand alone. They are objects built on their own initiative without anyone's knowledge or indication. The goal is to take great advantage of the development of this area.

This, in turn, is one of the most important factors for the development of Tourism. In the process of globalization today, the tourism sector is of particular importance in the economic activities of almost all countries as a high source of income. The influence of this industry on the economic social life of the country is

not only a key factor in the creation of currency revenue, jobs, the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, but also the preservation of cultures and values inherited from ancestors. Current trends in the development of Tourism indicate an increasing influence on both the world economy and the economy of individual countries and regions. Tourism is becoming a major independent sector of the national economy, carrying out activities aimed at meeting the needs of the population itself. Due to the variety of these needs, tourism is manifested as one of the factors that multiplicatively affect the development of the national economy complex, participating not only tourist enterprises, but also enterprises of other industries. In addition, tourism is one of the main needs of humans, which provides significant assistance to humans in the rapid development of technological development of Science, in reducing the emotional and psychological negative effects that arise as a result of labor intensity. In Uzbekistan, where the tourism industry is not sufficiently developed, unlike many countries, the development of the tourism industry requires an increase in cash receipts, lowering the unemployment rate, activating state regulatory processes as a direction to stabilize the socio-economic situation of the country, studying the tourist services market, expanding the tourist education system, developing programs that ensure the development of certain regions.

The implementation of the program "travel through Uzbekistan" has significantly influenced the development of tourist culture in the country. The total number of domestic tourists in the country exceeded 8.8 million in 2016 to 14.7 million in 2019 and 15 million in 2021. This was announced by the Ministry of Tourism and cultural heritage. Over the past 4 years, 833 new hotels have been commissioned in Uzbekistan: large, medium and small hotels. The total number of placement funds had grown to 1,442. In this case, the number of rooms — 33.4 thousand units, while the number of seats in it — was increased to 71.2. At the moment, hundreds of new hotel projects are being built in Uzbekistan, which are

planned to be put into operation in the near future. In March 2022, an analysis of statistics on the average employment of hotels and hostels of all categories in Uzbekistan showed positive changes. On March 28-30 – the three-day period load was more than 70.8 percent in the Republic, 83.6 percent in Tashkent, 62.3 percent in Samarkand, 93.9 percent in Karakalpakstan, 56.3 percent in Khorezm, and 46 percent in Bukhara. These are very good indicators, which indicate the growth of the tourism industry, and for the hotel business-a rapid recovery in profitability. In 2017, the employment rate of hotels was 39.3%, in 2019-53.1%, in the acute period of the pandemic – 22.1%, and last year the employment rate was 36.3%.

Analysis of the number of tourists in Uzbekistan in 2019-2022 shows a significant recovery dynamics, although in 2022 this figure is lagging by 15%, the number of rooms increased from 26,147 to 33,411, i.e. 7,264 hotel rooms (21.7 percent), compared to 2019. Among the guests of Uzbekistan, in addition to local tourists and citizens of the country, Russians — 23.4 percent, Kazakhs – 18.9 percent, Tajik – 14.4 percent, Turks — 7.7 percent. All foreigners living in hotels: Kyrgyz — 6.3 percent, Belarusians — 4.6 percent, Chinese — 3.2 percent, French — 1.7 percent. In the pre-pandemic period of 2019, 84.8 thousand foreign nationals lived, with the highest proportion of Russians — 16.8%, Kazakhs — 15%, Tajiks — 6.3%, Chinese — 6.1%, Afghans — 5.7%, Turks — 5.5%. At the moment, Uzbekistan is completely open to foreign tourists. All restrictions on this were removed. In Uzbekistan, positive trends are observed in the rapid recovery of the tourism sector, and the above figures indicate that up to 4.5 million foreign tourists will enter our country by the end of 2022.

In place of the conclusion , it can be said that today, in the development of the country's economy, the improvement of living conditions for the population, its emergence into the international arena and its worthy place in it, the role of the tourism industry, along with all spheres, is significant. Currently, in order to promote tourism among the people, the TV channels of our country show a variety

of travel shows that promote the tourism potential of Uzbekistan, various gadgets, tourist resorts, centers, unusual and Legendary Places of our Country Day and night, subsidies for the development of Tourism and other means of promotion are also used. Ambassadors in foreign countries should be propagandists of our country, national values, and our compatriots abroad should contribute to this.

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